

FIBER PRESTRESS APPLICATION IN MARINE STRUCTURES

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Analysis of the effect of fiber prestress release on overall response, local fields and damage resistance of composite laminates is a relatively new subject. Typically applied to reduce fiber waviness for improvement of compressive strength, fiber prestress may also create large residual stresses that either improve or diminish damage resistance of laminated composite plates and cylindrical shells. For example, application of constant fiber prestress in all plies of a cylindrical laminate creates high residual stress gradients that may impair the load bearing capacity of the structure loaded by external pressure in deep sea environment [1].

On the other hand, optimized prestress distributions can be found such that the residual stresses are minimized and the total mechanical and residual stresses are within allowable limits [2,3]. The presentation will review recent results on prestressing of cylindrical laminates and laminated plates with free edges, with emphasis on the effect of matrix viscous deformation or relaxation of the prestress-induced residual stresses in laminated plates [4].

The results are visualized by constructing damage envelopes in overall stress planes, consisting of ply branches that indicate satisfaction of selected strength criteria. The internal envelope of the branches indicates a damage-free loading range of the laminate.

This is illustrated in the Figure 1, which was constructed for $((0/90)_2/\bar{0})_s$ AS4/EPON laminate, using the Transformation Field Analysis method, which regards the viscous strains as eigenstrains applied to the original elastic laminate [5]. An optimized prestress distribution was found for a maximum amplitude of uniaxial tension, subject to constraints imposed by ply strength criteria. As the results show, fiber prestress causes both absolute and relative translations of the individual branches. The damage envelope is thus relocated to contain the prescribed loading program, and also substantially expanded, so that the laminate remains damage free when loaded by much larger biaxial stress amplitudes than those admissible in the absence of fiber prestress.

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Figure 1: Damage envelopes for the viscoelastic laminate before and after 12000 sec stress relaxation. The overall stress is applied with rate 1 MPa/sec (dotted line) and instantaneously (solid and dashed lines). Optimized fiber prestress is 2100 MPa in the 0-degree plies and 470.8 MPa in the 90-degree plies. Thermal change of -45C is applied at $t \geq 0$.

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